

A highly sensitive ratiometric optical thermometer based on Sr₂MgWO₆ double perovskite doped with Dy³⁺

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Keywords: double perovskite, dysprosium, co-precipitation method, relative sensitivity, optical thermometer, yellow-emitting phosphor

Abstract

The increasing demand for highly sensitive optical thermometers operating within a low-temperature range necessitates the development of efficient alternatives. In this work, a novel yellow-emitting phosphor, Sr₂MgWO₆ double perovskite, doped with varying concentrations of dysprosium (Dy³⁺) was synthesized *via* the coprecipitation method. Increasing the Dy³⁺ concentration from 0% to 7% shifted the color of luminescence from blue to yellowish-orange within the CIE1931 color space. Additionally, the energy transfer efficiency from the tungstate host to Dy³⁺ increased significantly to 98.4%. Moreover, the sample doped with 3% Dy³⁺ showed the highest emission intensity, with concentration beyond this inducing concentration quenching. This phenomenon is primarily governed by quadrupole-quadrupole interactions. Importantly, a fluorescence-based thermometry method utilizing the emission intensity ratio upon 266 nm excitation wavelength between the tungstate host and dopant emissions was developed. This approach offers self-referencing capability and highly sensitive temperature detection (above 0.4%/K) and very low temperature uncertainty (below 0.1 K) within the 80 K - 273 K range. Noticeably, the relative thermal sensitivity S_r reached the maximum of 3.24%/K, and temperature uncertainties δT were found to be 0.00368 K at 193 K. The maximum value of S_r decreases from 3.24%/K to 2.67%/K when the concentration of Dy³⁺ embedded in the lattice correspondingly increases from 3% to 7%. Our results not only provide insights into the luminescent characteristics of Dy³⁺-doped Sr₂MgWO₆ but also indicate a route towards achieving a highly sensitive ratiometric optical thermometer.

1. Introduction

Optical thermometers have garnered significant attention over the last decades since they offer numerous advantages, such as high accuracy, high reliability, high durability, and quick response compared with conventional sensors[1]. The optical thermometry can be designed based on the emission intensity of the two emission peaks, decay time, and a shift in emission peak. One of the most reliable and simplest methods is the ratiometric technique, so-called fluorescence intensity ratio (FIR), or luminescence intensity ratio (LIR). A significant

difference in the thermal dependency on the temperature of the two given emission peaks is a key parameter for achieving a highly sensitive luminescent thermometer.

Recent studies pointed out that double perovskite materials exhibit huge potential for thermal sensing application[2–6]. Among thousands of double perovskites, Sr_2MgWO_6 has been investigated mainly for crystal structure and phase transition[7–11], ceramic fabrication[12], and far-red[13]/near-infrared luminescence[14] while the possibility of working as an optical thermometer is unintentionally neglected. The tungstate groups WO_6 have been reported to efficiently absorb near UV, exhibit an asymmetric broad emission band from 345 to 540 nm[15–18], and is beneficial for designing a ratiometric luminescent thermometer, such as WO_6 and Ho^{3+} [19], Eu^{3+} [16], Nd^{3+} [5], Er^{3+} [17].

In this study, dysprosium is selected to embed in our matrices. Generally, emission spectrum of Dy^{3+} consists of three main transitions located in the visible region including a blue emission (${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{15/2}$ transition), yellow emission (${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{13/2}$ transition), and red emission (${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{11/2}$ transition). Of which the yellow line at around 575 nm is of interest for both phosphors and laser applications. Particularly, the proportion between the intensity of the yellow and blue emission bands (Y/B ratio) depends on the host lattice which has been extensively investigated to realize single phase white light emitting phosphors[20].

For temperature sensing application, due to the fact, that the tungstate host and the dopant have different thermal stabilities. Thanks to this, the simultaneous emissions of the host and the dopant in the spectrum offers a self-referencing optical thermometer with highly sensitivity in a low-temperature range[5,16,17,19]. Especially, the thermally coupled levels of Dy^{3+} (${}^4\text{I}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{15/2}$ and ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{15/2}$) were utilized for FIR-based temperature sensing since these levels are separately by approximately 1000 cm^{-1} . Dy^{3+} is suitable for thermometry operating at high temperature.

To the best of the authors knowledge, only one study on SMW doped with 2% Dy^{3+} has been studied for . Therefore, this study mainly focused on the luminescent properties and potential applications of a novel double perovskite Sr_2MgWO_6 doped with Dy^{3+} in terms of white-light emitting phosphor and temperature detection.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and synthesis

For the first time, a series of double perovskites $\text{Sr}_2\text{Mg}_{1.2-2x}\text{Dy}_x\text{Li}_x\text{WO}_6$ (abbreviated as SMW) was synthesized using the co-precipitation method, with varying concentration of Dy^{3+} ($x = 0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7\%$). To compensate the loss of Mg due to evaporation during high-temperature sintering, a surplus of 20% molar excess $\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ was introduced during the synthesis process. Lithium was employed as a charge compensator to uphold charge balance, as depicted by the equation $\text{Dy}^{3+} + \text{Li}^+ \rightarrow 2\text{Mg}^{2+}$. The amounts of precursor materials were determined to yield a final product with a total mass of 0.5 g.

The precursors utilized in the syntheses consist of strontium acetate $\text{Sr}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar, 99%), magnesium acetate $\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar, 99.95%), ammonium paratungstate $(\text{NH}_4)_{10}\text{H}_2(\text{W}_2\text{O}_7)_6$ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), dysprosium oxide Dy_2O_3 (Alfa Aesar, 99.99%), and lithium carbonate Li_2CO_3 (Alfa Aesar, 99.998%), nitric acid HNO_3 (POCH, 65%). All the precursors were used without any further purification.

Initially, solution A containing tungstate ions, and solution B containing strontium and magnesium, were individually dissolved in 20 ml of distilled water. Subsequently, dysprosium oxide was dissolved into a nitric acid solution to generate a dysprosium nitrate solution (equivalent to 1.67×10^{-5} mol Dy³⁺ per ml). The stoichiometric quantity of Dy³⁺ was then introduced into solution B. Afterward, solution A was gradually introduced into solution B under mild agitation using a magnetic stirrer operating at 200 rpm at room temperature. After that, the resulting white precipitate was subjected to drying at 80°C for 24 hours. Following the drying process, the precipitate underwent two cycles of annealing in an air environment within a corundum crucible. The initial sintering stage occurred at 600°C for 12 hours. And the subsequent sintering process was identified at 1150°C for 6 hours, with a controlled heating rate of 3°C per minute.

2.2.Characterizations

The X-ray powder diffraction analysis was employed to verify the purity of the synthesized samples. This measurement was performed using the X'Pert PRO powder diffractometer from PANalytical in the Netherlands, equipped with a linear PIXcel detector and CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$), covering the 2θ range of 10° to 70°. To record diffuse reflection spectra, a Varian Cary 5E UV/VIS-NIR spectrophotometer (Varian Incorporation, Palo Alto, USA) was utilized. The emission decay profiles were observed using a Tektronix MD3052 mixed domain oscilloscope (500 MHz, Beaverton, USA) along with an Nd: YAG laser from Teledyne LeCroy (New York, USA). Furthermore, temperature-dependent luminescent spectra were analysed using the Hamamatsu photonic multichannel analyser PMA-12, fitted with a BT-CCD linear image sensor from Hamamatsu Photonics K.K in Shizuoka, Japan. The samples' temperature during these assessments was regulated using a Linkam THMS 600 Heating/Freezing Stage from The McCrone Group (Westmont, USA).

3. Results and discussions

3.1.Structure

Figure 1. a) X-ray powder diffraction lines of Sr_2MgWO_6 : $x\%\text{Dy}^{3+}$, $x\%\text{Li}^+$ ($x = 0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7\%$); b) The dependence of unit cell volume on the concentration of Dy^{3+} ions; c) Visualization of crystal structure of SMW (ICSD #152574).

The X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns of all samples exhibit a strong agreement with the standard patterns ICSD #152574 (refer to Figure 1 a). No additional phases were detected in the analysis.

Furthermore, the relationship between the content of Dy^{3+} ions and the unit cell volume of matrix is illustrated in Figure 1b. This graph clearly demonstrates that as the concentration of Dy^{3+} ions increases, the unit cell volume (calculated through the indexing method) also increases. Specifically, for SMW doped with 0.1% Dy^{3+} and 7% Dy^{3+} , the unit cell volume expands from 247.33 \AA^3 to 248.08 \AA^3 , respectively. This significant observation implies the successful substitution of larger ions (Dy^{3+} CN = 6, $r = 105.2 \text{ pm}$)[21] in the place of Mg^{2+} (CN = 6, $r = 86 \text{ pm}$)[21] within the host lattice.

In Figure 1c, the crystal structure of SMW is depicted. Although recent studies indicated a cubic structure for SMW[22,23], our investigation revealed a consistent tetragonal crystal structure for all prepared samples, conforming to the $I4/m$ (87) space group. The lattice parameters were determined as follows: $a = 5.5849 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.5849 \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 7.9455 \text{ \AA}$. In the structure, the $[\text{MgO}_6]$ and $[\text{WO}_6]$ octahedra are constructed by the coordination of six oxygen atoms each at the Mg^{2+} and W^{6+} sites (C_{4h}), respectively. Simultaneously, the $[\text{SrO}_{12}]$ polyhedral structure is formed as the Sr^{2+} site (S_4) coordinates with 12 oxygen atoms. These polyhedra are intricately interconnected, constituting the robust rock-salt double perovskite structure.

3.2. Optical bandgaps

To determine the bandgaps of synthesized materials, the diffuse reflectance spectra of the SMW host and SMW doped with 1%Dy³⁺ and 7%Dy³⁺ are presented in Figure 2. It can be seen that the samples exhibit a strong absorption edge in the range of 250 to 350 nm, which can be attributed to the O²⁻ - W⁶⁺ charge transfer band[24].

According to the literature[25], the Tauc equation is given by $\alpha(h\nu) \approx B(h\nu - E_g)^n$ (1) where α represents the extinction coefficient, h is Planck's constant (J.s), ν is the frequency of light (s⁻¹), n depends on the nature of compound, $n = 1/2$ for direct and $n = 2$ for indirect material. B is the absorption constant, E_g is bandgap energy (eV).

The equation (1) was rewritten using the Kubelka-Munk function, where α was replaced with $F(R)$, $F(R) = \frac{(1-R)^2}{2R}$, (2) with R being the reflectance. Since the investigated compounds belong to the indirect semiconductor type[17], the value $n = 2$ was used for the calculation. The bandgap energies were estimated by extrapolating the intercept of the fitted straight line at $F(R) = 0$ in the plot of $(F \times hv)^{1/2}$ versus energy ($h\nu$) (Figure 2, inset).

The bandgaps of the SMW host, and SMW doped with 1%Dy³⁺, and 7%Dy³⁺ samples decreases from 3.83 eV to 3.78 eV and then 3.73 eV with an increase in Dy³⁺ concentration. This phenomenon is similar to the one observed in Ba₂MgWO₆ doped with 0.1%Eu³⁺ (4.02 eV), and 5%Eu³⁺ (3.82 eV). Additionally, these obtained values are comparable to those of Ba₂MgWO₆:4%Er³⁺ (3.74 eV), Ca₂MgWO₆ host (3.98 eV),[24] and Sr₂CaWO₆ (3.91 eV)[26], indicating that Sr₂MgWO₆ can be employed as a luminescent material.

Figure 2. Diffuse reflectance spectra of Sr₂MgWO₆:x%Dy³⁺, x%Li⁺ (x = 0, 1, 7%) samples. Inset: Energy bandgaps estimated using the Kubelka-Munk function

3.3. Luminescent properties

The 300 K emission spectra upon the excitation of 266 nm of SMW:xDy are presented in Figure 3. In addition to a broad band of host emission spanning from 350 to 440 nm, four distinct emission peaks corresponding to the transitions of ⁴F_{9/2} → ⁶H_{15/2},

${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$, ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{11/2}$, ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{9/2}$ are observed at 480.5, 574.6, 664.3, and 752.79 nm, respectively. The more concentration of Dy^{3+} introduced in the host, the more intense yellow emission (${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$) is obtained. With an increase in Dy^{3+} concentration in the host, there is a corresponding enhancement in the intensity of the yellow emission (${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$). Simultaneously, the emission intensity of the host diminishes noticeably with increasing Dy^{3+} ion concentration, as shown in the inset on the left side of the figure. This decrease in host emission intensity is indicative of an efficient energy transfer process from $[WO_6]$ to the Dy^{3+} ions. To quantify this energy transfer efficiency (η_{ET}), the following equation is applied:

$$\eta_{ET} = 1 - \frac{I_S}{I_{S0}} \quad (3)$$

where I_S , I_{S0} is the integrated emission intensities of the samples with activator (Dy^{3+}) and without activator, respectively.

The sample doped with the highest Dy^{3+} concentration (7%) exhibits the most effective energy transfer, while the sample with the lowest doping concentration of Dy^{3+} (0.1%) demonstrates the least efficient energy transfer.

Figure 3. 300 K emission spectra of $Sr_2MgWO_6:x\%Dy^{3+}$, $x\%Li^+$ ($x = 0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7\%$) excited at 266 nm. Inset: Emission intensity of the host, the energy transfer efficiency as a function of Dy^{3+} concentration

The integrated emission intensity of all samples as a function of Dy³⁺ concentration is presented in Figure 4a. The strongest emission intensity is achieved for the sample doped with 3% Dy³⁺. Beyond this concentration, the emission intensity decreases significantly due to concentration quenching. To verify the primary interaction between Dy³⁺-Dy³⁺ ions responsible for this quenching phenomenon, the critical distance R_C was calculated. If the value of R_C is smaller than 5 Å, the main mechanism is the exchange interaction. Otherwise, the dominant interaction is multipolar interaction including dipole-dipole (d-d), dipole-quadrupole (d-q), quadrupole-quadrupole interaction (q-q).

The critical distance (R_C) between Dy³⁺ ions is determined by the following equation[27]:

$$R_C = 2 \times \left(\frac{3V}{4\pi X_C N} \right)^{1/3} \quad (4)$$

where V is the volume of a unit cell, X_C is the concentration for which the highest emission intensity is obtained, and N is the number of lattice sites in the unit cell which can be substituted by Dy³⁺ ions. For SMW:3%Dy³⁺, $V = 247.36 \text{ \AA}^3$, $X_C = 0.03$, $N = 2$. The critical distance between Dy³⁺ ions was found to be 19.9 Å. Therefore, the concentration quenching phenomenon was mainly regulated by an electric multipole-multipole interaction. The relationship between the emission intensity and dopant concentration is exhibited through the Dexter equation[28]:

$$\frac{I}{x} = k \times (1 + \beta(x)^{Q/3})^{-1} \quad (5)$$

where I is the integrated emission intensity of Dy³⁺, x is the concentration of Dy³⁺, k and β are constants, and $Q = 6, 8, 10$ represents for the d-d, d-q, and q-q interaction, respectively.

From the equation (5), the relationship between $\log(x)$ and $\log(I/x)$ is presented as follow:

$$\log\left(\frac{I}{x}\right) = C - \left(\frac{Q}{3}\right) \log(x) \quad (6)$$

From the linear fitting, the value of Q is around 11 (Figure 4b), indicating that the concentration quenching phenomenon of Dy³⁺ ions is predominantly governed by quadrupole-quadrupole interaction. This finding is very similar to the ones obtained for Sr₃MoO₆:Eu³⁺[29], Sr₂InTaO₆:Eu³⁺[30], Ba₂YSbO₆:Eu³⁺, Ba₃Y₄O₉:Eu³⁺[31].

Figure 4. a) Integrated emission intensity of all samples as a function of Er³⁺ concentration at 300 K; b) Relationship between log(x) and log(I/x) of samples Sr₂MgWO₆:x%Dy³⁺, x%Li⁺, (x = 3, 5, 7%); c) The CIE 1931 chromaticity diagram with the coordinates (x,y) of Sr₂MgWO₆:x%Dy³⁺, x%Li⁺ as a function of Dy³⁺ concentration at room temperature.

The Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage (CIE) 1931 chromaticity coordinates presented in Figure 4b illustrate the influence of Dy³⁺ concentration on the emitted light. It can be seen that the coordinates vary with distinct Dy³⁺ concentrations, shifting from the bluish-violet region (SMW host) to yellowish-orange (SMW:0.1%Dy³⁺), and then to a more orange color for further increasing Dy³⁺ concentration due to the greater distortion of the octahedral of Dy³⁺ in the lattice, which increases the yellow-to-blue ratio. The detailed values of CIE are presented in Table S1.

To examine the potential of this phosphor for lighting applications, the thermal stability of phosphor should be taken into account. The temperature-dependent emission spectra of the sample doped with 3%Dy³⁺ ions were investigated over the range of 80 K to 673 K, as depicted in Figure S1. As a key parameter, the quenching temperature ($T_{0.5}$) denotes the temperature at which the emission intensity drops by 50%. As exhibited in the inset of Figure S1, the integrated emission intensity drops with the elevated temperature, demonstrating the thermal quenching phenomenon. In detail, the emission intensity at 153 K is approximately half that at 80 K. Besides, no plateau is observed in the emission intensity versus temperature function, the quenching temperature $T_{0.5}$ could not be determined for this compound, similar to the case of Ba₂MgWO₆:Er³⁺[17]. It is of course lower than 153 K, which is much lower than that measured for the potential phosphor NaLaMgWO₆:Er³⁺ ($T_{0.5} = 403 \text{ K}$)[32]. The low thermal stability renders our material unsuitable as a reliable phosphor for solid-state lighting.

Additionally, the temperature dependence of the emission intensity was described using the Arrhenius equation below[33].

$$I = \frac{I_0}{1 + e^{-\Delta E_a / (k_B T)}} \quad (7)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant, I_0 is the initial intensity, I is the intensity corresponding to different temperature T , ΔE_a is activation energy

The relationship between $[\ln(I_0/I)-1]$ and $[1/(k_B T)]$ is presented in Figure S2. The experimental data were fitted linearly, from where the activation energy was derived.

3.4. Decay profiles

Figure 5. 300 K luminescence decay curves of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MgWO}_6:x\%\text{Dy}^{3+}$, $x\%\text{Li}^+$ ($x = 0.1\%$ and 7%)

The 300 K emission decay profiles of Dy^{3+} ions, monitored at 574 nm (the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{13/2}$ transition) was analyzed upon excitation at 266 nm (Figure 5).

As can be seen, all the decay curves show non-exponential behaviors and were well-fitted with the following function:

$$y = y_0 + A_1 e^{-x/\tau_1} + A_2 e^{-x/\tau_2} \quad (8)$$

where y_0 is the offset, A_1 , A_2 are the amplitudes, and τ_1 , τ_2 are the decay times. The average decay time was calculated using the provided formula:

$$\tau_{avg} = \frac{A_1 \times \tau_1^2 + A_2 \times \tau_2^2}{A_1 + A_2} \quad (9)$$

The emission lifetime gradually shortens from 141 μs to 112 μs with an increase in Dy^{3+} concentration from 0.1% to 7% Dy^{3+} , respectively. With a higher concentration of Dy^{3+} ions in the sample, the distance between the Dy^{3+} ions decreases, leading to a higher probability of occurrence of nonradiative processes. Further details of the emission decay times can be found in Table S2.

The obtained lifetimes in this study are significantly shorter than those found in Ba₂MgWO₆:Dy[34] (450 μs) and in Ba₂CaWO₆:Dy[35] (546 μs). Such short lifetimes observed in the investigated double perovskites results from the very low activation energy (ΔE_a = 0.0383 eV, see Figure S2).

3.5. Temperature sensing performance

Due to the strong overlap between the emission of Dy³⁺ and the host emission (see Figure S3), only samples doped with 3, 5, and 7% Dy³⁺ ions were explored for luminescent temperature sensing. Their temperature-dependent emission spectra in the range of 80 – 273 K are presented in Figure 6a, S4a, and S5a, respectively. The normalized emission intensities of the host and all transitions of Dy³⁺ of the sample doped with 3% Dy³⁺ as a function of temperature are also shown in Figure 6b. As can be seen in Figure 6b, S4b, and S5b, the integrated emission intensity of the host drops dramatically by the elevated temperature and almost quenches at 300 K. The integrated emission intensity of the ⁴F_{9/2} → ⁶H_{15/2} transition behaves similarly to the host with respect to the temperature. Moreover, as the temperature increased up to 200 K, there was a significant 90% drop in the integrated emission intensities of the host and the ⁴F_{9/2} → ⁶H_{15/2} transition. While the other Dy³⁺ transitions show a gradual reduction in emission intensity, decreased by 50% at 300 K for SMW:3%Dy³⁺, 213 K for SMW:5%, and 193 K 7%Dy³⁺ compared with their initial values at 80 K, and eventually maintain 50%, 40% and 30% of the integrated emission intensities at 300 K, respectively.

Therefore, the temperature sensing abilities of these samples are investigated based on the fluorescent intensity ratios (FIR) of the integrated emission intensity of Dy³⁺ transitions and of the host. Four channels (FIRs) are chosen as follows:

$$FIR_{21} = \frac{I_2}{I_1} = \frac{I_{465-511}}{I_{345-465} + I_{511-556}} \quad (10)$$

$$FIR_{31} = \frac{I_3}{I_1} = \frac{I_{556-640}}{I_{345-465} + I_{511-556}} \quad (11)$$

$$FIR_{41} = \frac{I_4}{I_1} = \frac{I_{640-730}}{I_{345-465} + I_{511-556}} \quad (12)$$

$$FIR_{51} = \frac{I_5}{I_1} = \frac{I_{730-800}}{I_{345-465} + I_{511-556}} \quad (13)$$

where I is the integrated emission intensity of the related emission band/peak.

Figure 6. a) Temperature - dependent emission spectra of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MgWO}_6:3\%\text{Dy}^{3+}, 3\%\text{Li}^+$ ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 266 \text{ nm}$); b) Emission spectra of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MgWO}_6:3\%\text{Dy}^{3+}, 3\%\text{Li}^+$ at 80 K and 273 K and five areas are evaluated for thermometry; c) Normalized emission intensity of the host and Dy^{3+} transitions as a function of temperature.

In Figure 6d, the relationship between FIR and the sample's temperature was fitted using the following equation[36]

$$\text{FIR} = A + \frac{B}{1+C \times \exp\left(\frac{D}{T}\right)} \quad (14)$$

where A, B, C, D are constants, T represents the temperature.

All FIR curves exhibit similar behavior, the Dy^{3+} transition-to-host ratio increases with rising temperature (Figure S6 a-c). This trend indicates that the effective energy transfer from the host to the Dy^{3+} ions is enhanced by temperature. Besides, the most significant change occurred for the sample doped with 3% Dy^{3+} and the less change belongs to the sample doped with 7% Dy^{3+} . Fitting these FIR curves with the aforementioned function aims to calculate the temperature uncertainty in the subsequent discussion.

The thermometer's response to temperature changes was assessed using the thermometric parameters, including the absolute sensitivity (S_a, K^{-1}) and the relative thermal sensitivity ($S_r, \%/K$), calculated using the following equations.

$$S_a = \left| \frac{\partial \text{FIR}}{\partial T} \right| \quad (15)$$

$$S_r = 100\% \times \left| \frac{1}{\Delta} \frac{\partial \text{FIR}}{\partial T} \right| \quad (16)$$

Overall, a consistent tendency across all channels. The absolute sensitivities S_a initially increases with rising temperature up to 233 K (observed for $\text{SMW}:3\%\text{Dy}^{3+}$), 253 K (for $\text{SMW}:5\%\text{Dy}^{3+}$), and 273 K ($\text{SMW}:7\%\text{Dy}^{3+}$); beyond this threshold, they decrease (refer to

Figure S6 d-f.). The maximum S_a value of the sample doped with 3% is the highest (0.314 K^{-1}), followed by SMW:5%Dy³⁺ (0.143 K^{-1}), and SMW:7%Dy³⁺ (0.06 K^{-1}).

Similarly, the relative sensitivities S_r exhibit an increase with temperature (Figure 7 a-c). The highest relative thermal sensitivities are achieved for the channel FIR51 (the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$ transition and the host). Increasing the Dy³⁺ concentration from 3% to 7%, the maximum S_r (at 193 K) decreases from 3.24%/K, 3.22%/K, to 2.67%/K, respectively. Other channels (FIR₃₁, FIR₄₁) also demonstrate notably high sensitivities at the same temperature of 193 K. The exception is FIR₂₁, with a shifting maximum S_r value of 1.68%/K (213 K), 1.47%/K (233 K), and 1.33%/K (233 K) are obtained for SMW doped with 3%, 5%, and 7% Dy³⁺, respectively. In general, the relative thermal sensitivities remain above 0.4%/K throughout the investigated temperature range.

To comprehensively characterize the temperature sensing capability of the samples, the temperature uncertainties δT (K) as a function of temperature (Fig. 7 d-f) were calculated using the equation[37]

$$\delta T = \frac{1}{S_r} \frac{\delta \text{FIR}}{\text{FIR}} \quad (17)$$

where δFIR represents the fluctuations of FIR due to changes in temperature.

The calculated temperature measurement uncertainty is below 0.1 K across the entire investigated temperature range. As temperature increases, there is a simultaneous decrease in the value of δT . The sample doped with 3%Dy³⁺ shows little higher uncertainty values as compared to the other samples.

Figure 7. Relative sensitivity S_r (%/K) of SMW: $x\% \text{Dy}^{3+}$, $x\% \text{Li}^+$ where $x = 3\%$ (a), $x = 5\%$ (b), $x = 7\%$ (c); Temperature uncertainty δT (K) of SMW: $x\% \text{Dy}^{3+}$, $x\% \text{Li}^+$ where $x = 3\%$ (d), $x = 5\%$ (e), $x = 7\%$ (f) as a function of temperature from 80 – 273 K.

Furthermore, the reproducibility of temperature measurements was evaluated, demonstrating a consistent accuracy of more than 99% across six cycles between 80 and 273 K (see Figure S7).

To fully evaluate the temperature sensing performance of the optical thermometers, the relative sensitivity, and the temperature uncertainty (if available), as well as the operating temperature range of some representative temperature sensing materials are collated in Table 1. It should be mentioned that a significant advantage of S_r is its suitability for quantitative comparisons across different types of optical thermometers. As evident from the literature, the prevailing focus is on high-temperature working ranges, typically exceeding 300 K. In contrast, our sample, SMW:3%Dy³⁺ with the maximum S_r of 3.24%/K is the most prospective temperature sensing material offering a wide working range at low temperatures coupled with minimal temperature uncertainty. This comprehensive comparison reaffirms SMW's potential as an optical thermometer in the low-temperature region.

Table 1. The maximum relative sensitivities S_r at the given temperature T, working temperature range, and temperature uncertainty δT of Dy³⁺-based optical thermometers

Material	Temperature range (K)	S_r (%K ⁻¹)	T (K)	δT (K)	Reference
MgNb ₂ O ₆ :Pr, Dy	300 – 540	7.61	300	0.0045	[38]
Sr ₂ MgWO ₆ :Dy	80 – 273	3.24	193	0.0037	This study
La ₂ MgTiO ₆ :Mn, Dy	298 – 498	2.85	448	-	[2]
La ₂ MgTiO ₆ :Pr, Dy	298 – 548	2.357	498	-	[39]
YAG:Dy, Cr	200 – 700	2.2	200	-	[40]
BaYF ₅ :Dy	293 – 773	2	293	-	[41]
YNbO ₄ :Dy	293 – 773	1.97	300	-	[42]
SrWO ₄ : Eu, Dy	11 – 592	1.71	335	-	[43]
YAG:Ti, Dy	123 – 523	1.6	373	-	[44]
GdPO ₄ :Dy	290 – 539	1.55	290	-	[45]
CaYAlO ₄ :Dy	300 – 600	1.4	300	-	[46]
GdAl ₂ (BO ₃) ₄ :Dy, Eu	300 – 475	1.37	475	-	[47]
Li ₃ Y ₃ Te ₂ O ₁₂ :Dy	80-300	1.2	80	-	[48]
Sc ₂ W ₃ O ₁₂ :Dy	298 – 575	0.71	375	-	[49]

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the yellow-emitting phosphor series, Sr₂MgWO₆:x%Dy³⁺x%Li³⁺ double perovskites (where x = 0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7%) has been synthesized by using the coprecipitation method for the first time. The results reveals that Dy³⁺ ions were substituted within the Mg²⁺ site in the host lattice, resulting in yellow emission spectra due to the low symmetry crystallographic site (C_{4h}). The most intense emission intensity was observed in the SMW:3%Dy³⁺ sample. The concentration quenching phenomenon is primarily driven by quadrupole-quadrupole interaction between Dy³⁺ ions. Notably, as the Dy³⁺ concentration increased from 0.1% to 7%, the energy transfer efficiency to Dy³⁺ ions witnessed a substantial

rise from 85% to 98.3%, accompanied by a shift in chromaticity coordinates towards the yellowish-orange region on the chromaticity diagram. With an increase in content of Dy³⁺ ions, the closer distance between them led to a shortened decay time of emission due to increased nonradiative processes. Due to low thermal stability, this material is not recommended for lighting application. Furthermore, at 193 K, a maximum relative sensitivity S_r of 3.24%/K was achieved, along with a temperature uncertainty δT below 0.1 K in the whole operating temperature range (80 – 273 K). These findings emphasize the potential of studied materials for temperature determination at low temperatures.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the Polish National Science Centre under PRELUDIUM20 grant no. 2021/41/N/ST5/02385.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

The data presented in this study are openly available in Zenodo at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10781309

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